

High-quality deepfakes have a heart!

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2 ABSTRACT

3 Deepfakes have become ubiquitous in our modern society and the number of manipulated
4 videos and news stories on the internet are increasing. The current evolution of image generation
5 techniques makes the detection of manipulated content through visible inspection increasingly
6 difficult. This motivated researchers to analyze various signal properties for automatic deepfake
7 detection. Among others, the complexity of heart rate dynamics in the video is used to distinguish
8 between real videos and deepfakes. In particular, these signals are extracted from facial video
9 streams through remote photoplethysmography (rPPG). The current state of the art assumption
10 is that these subtle semantic signals get lost in the deepfake generation process and can thus be
11 used for deepfake detection. This paper presents a study proving that this assumption is no longer
12 valid for the current generation of deepfakes. To this end, we present a pipeline that extracts
13 heart rate signals from the captured rPPG signals and show that current deepfake generation
14 processes encapsulate the rPPG signal of the driving video sequence. For this, we captured
15 a dataset of facial videos in synchrony with an electrocardiogram (ECG) as ground truth pulse
16 signal. For deepfakes generated on this dataset, we show that (i) the deepfake video shows
17 valid heart rate dynamic and that (ii) these match with those of the underlying source videos.
18 Furthermore, we show that this also holds for deepfakes from a publicly available dataset.

19 **Keywords:** deepfakes, video forensics, remote photoplethysmography (rPPG), biological signals, remote heart rate estimation, imaging
20 photoplethysmography (iPPG)

1 INTRODUCTION

21 In recent years, deepfakes have emerged as a prominent and concerning phenomenon. Notably, political
22 figures such as Barack Obama, Donald Trump, and Wladimir Klitschko have become targets, drawing
23 significant public attention. The societal and ethical implications of deepfake technology have become
24 increasingly evident. Initial examples were characterized by visible artifacts, particularly when static images
25 were synthesized into video sequences (DeepFakes, 2019). However, advancements in image generation
26 techniques have significantly improved the realism of these manipulations, making it increasingly difficult
27 to detect alterations through visual inspection alone (Ramesh et al., 2021; Karras et al., 2020).

28 Modern state-of-the-art deepfake detection approaches rely on features learned by convolutional filters
29 sensitive to inconsistencies in both the spatial and the temporal domain (Wang et al., 2023; Haliassos
30 et al., 2022). Despite receiving outstanding performance results on benchmark datasets, these techniques
31 suffer from a lack of explainability. This weakness becomes critical when human supervisors of video-
32 identification systems face potential misclassifications by these detectors, leading to challenges due to their
33 opaque decision-making processes.

34 However, contemporary deepfake generation techniques, while increasingly sophisticated in their ability
35 to visually mimic real individuals, do not explicitly model physiological signals present in genuine videos.
36 The cardiovascular pulse, inducing individual pulsating blood flow in human skin, causes subtle color
37 variations that are assumed to be plausible in genuine videos only. This inadequacy has been employed by
38 several researchers for leveraging locally resolved signals, such as those captured by techniques like remote
39 photoplethysmography (rPPG), which capture these subtle variations (Yu et al., 2021a). For example, rPPG
40 can extract physiological information, such as pulse rate, from a recorded video, providing valuable data for
41 deepfake detection Kossack et al. (2019a). Traditional approaches have primarily focused on extracting a
42 global pulse signal from an entire video sequence (Yu et al., 2021a). Detectors leveraging this global rPPG
43 signal have demonstrated promising results concluding that deepfakes do not include such physiologically
44 induced signals. However, contrary findings indicate that deepfakes can indeed exhibit a one-dimensional
45 signal resembling a heart rate (HR), further complicating the detection process (Fernandes et al., 2019).
46 Additionally, recent advancements in synthetic face generation explicitly incorporate pulsation signals
47 (Ciftci and Yin, 2019) or enable the manipulation of physiological signals in facial videos (Chen et al.,
48 2022), thus blurring the distinction between real and fake rPPG signals. It is also important to note that
49 rPPG-based deepfake detectors may inadvertently rely on non-physiological cues, such as background
50 artifacts, noise, or comparisons between image pairs, rather than purely detecting pulse-related color
51 changes in the skin (Çiftçi et al., 2024; Qi et al., 2020; Ciftci et al., 2020b,a). For instance, Ciftci et al.
52 (2020a) demonstrated that filtering rPPG signals with a bandpass filter between 4.68 Hz to 15 Hz (i.e.,
53 180 bpm to 900 bpm), can more effectively distinguish real videos from deepfakes compared to filtering
54 signals based on human heart rate frequencies. This highlights a critical limitation in current deepfake
55 detection approaches that rely on rPPG signals, as they often fail to account for the fact that deepfakes can
56 still produce realistic HR signals.

57 In this paper, we demonstrate that HR signals can indeed be derived from deepfake videos, and, more
58 importantly, these signals closely match those of the original driving video, which define the head
59 motion and facial expressions. This finding challenges the assumption that deepfakes inherently lack valid
60 physiological signals and emphasizes the need for detection methods that go beyond simple pulse detection.
61 Our contribution provides new insights into the physiological consistency of deepfakes, raising the bar for
62 future detection techniques.

63 To validate our findings, we propose a pipeline that extracts the pulse rate from videos while incorporating
64 motion compensation and background noise reduction for enhanced robustness. To further substantiate
65 our approach, we collected a dataset consisting of video recordings synchronized with electrocardiogram
66 (ECG) data. Our experiments demonstrate that the HRs extracted from the videos using our pipeline closely
67 align with those from the ECG signal, confirming the accuracy of the rPPG-based extraction process. To
68 explore the origin of the heart beats detected in the rPPG signals of the deepfake videos, we generated a set
69 of deepfakes based on these original video recordings. In our experiments, we show that the HRs derived
70 from the deepfakes significantly overlap with those of the source (or ‘driver’) videos, highlighting that
71 deepfake HR signals are not random but rather reflect the physiological information present in the driving

72 video. Furthermore, we extend our analysis to older generations of deepfakes by utilizing the publicly
73 available KoDF dataset (Kwon et al., 2021), where we similarly demonstrate the presence of valid HR
74 signals. These results emphasize that even older deepfake methods can carry realistic physiological signals,
75 further complicating traditional detection methods.

76 The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, we provide an overview of existing
77 work on deepfake generation, deepfake detection, and rPPG. Our proposed method is presented in Section 3.
78 Section 4 outlines the experiments conducted, along with the presentation of our used dataset and results.
79 Thereafter, we discuss our method's limitations and conclude our paper with a summary of our results and
80 findings in Section 6.

2 RELATED WORK

81 2.1 Deepfakes

82 Deepfakes represent a category of manipulated videos and audio files created through deep learning
83 techniques. These manipulations involve altering faces, modifying gestures and facial expressions, and
84 adjusting physical appearances and mouth movements to align with manipulated audio content. The
85 widespread popularity of deepfakes is evident in various applications, with common usage found in AI-
86 based face swapping techniques. Notably, there is a surge in popularity with smartphone apps that facilitate
87 seamless face swapping, demonstrating the accessibility and user-friendly nature of these technologies.
88 These apps leverage advanced voice synthesis, facial synthesis, and video generation methods to produce
89 convincing and often deceptive content.

90 The development of GANs (Goodfellow et al., 2014), VAEs (Kingma and Welling, 2014) and, lately,
91 diffusion models (Ho et al., 2020) enabled various possibilities for the forgery of digital content. The
92 seminal deepfake generation method utilizes a dual-decoder autoencoder, with each decoder dedicated to
93 one of the set target identities for swapping (DeepFakes, 2019). Subsequently, this foundational method has
94 been enhanced by the integration of adversarial training, application of more sophisticated convolutional
95 neural networks or advanced blending techniques (Perov et al., 2020; Beckmann et al., 2023). Numerous
96 methods have been developed for manipulating face expressions and appearances, with modern approaches
97 capable of synthesizing a face with a given appearance and an expression of choice in the one-shot
98 scenario (Drobyshv et al., 2022; Nirkin et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2021b,a). Recently, several approaches
99 leverage denoising diffusion models for the generation and manipulation of high-quality face images
100 (Ho et al., 2020; Zhao et al., 2023; Ding et al., 2023; Huang et al., 2023). This continuous evolution of
101 deepfake technologies poses challenges for content authentication and necessitates the development of
102 robust detection mechanisms.

103 Early approaches to detect deepfakes exploit physical inconsistencies in the behaviour and appearance of
104 the head. Li et al. (2018) exploit the fact that early deepfake generation approaches merely use training
105 images with opened eyes, by utilizing facial landmarks to identify the eye-blinking behaviour in videos. In
106 Yang et al. (2019), the authors take advantage of the fact that the process of cropping, aligning and inserting
107 a face onto another head leads to a misalignment of the attributes in the inner face and the head pose. Other
108 approaches aim to manually generate fake training images by simulating the artifacts introduced by warping
109 or blending operations in genuine images (Li and Lyu, 2018; Li et al., 2020). With the rapid increase
110 of quality in visual fake content, research focus shifted from more obvious and explainable artifacts to
111 high dimensional complex convolutional feature maps. In the foundational FaceForensics++ (FF++) paper

112 (Rössler et al., 2019), the authors propose a benchmark dataset for the evaluation of deepfake detectors and
113 analyze the detection performance of several CNN based detectors.

114 While recent and ongoing works on generating better deepfakes focus mostly on making them look
115 more realistic and appealing, the coherence of biological rPPG signals is not considered. This motivated
116 several researches to work on the promising line of fake detection methods, analyzing the coherence
117 of biological rPPG signals in the spatial and temporal domain and thereby increasing the explainability
118 of the detection process (Ciftci et al., 2020a; Hernandez-Ortega et al., 2020). FakeCatcher (Ciftci et al.,
119 2020a) extracts rPPG signals from three face regions which are subject to various signal transformations.
120 Moreover, the extracted signals are consolidated into image-like PPG maps, which represent the temporal
121 and spatial distribution of biological signals across the analyzed facial regions. Those signal maps are then
122 fed to a CNN for classification. DeepFakeON-Phys (Hernandez-Ortega et al., 2020) adapts the heart rate
123 estimation method proposed in Chen and McDuff (2018) and modifies it through the usage of a two branch
124 convolutional attention network to assess both appearance and motion related information for deepfake
125 video detection. In Wu et al. (2023), the authors propose the usage of a temporal transformer in combination
126 with a mask-guided local attention module in order to capture spatial and temporal inconsistencies over
127 long distances in the used PPG maps. Detection methods that specifically pay attention to the heart rate
128 (HR) information extracted from rPPG were proposed in Ciftci et al. (2020b); Boccignone et al. (2022).

129 **2.2 rPPG**

130 The extraction of human vital signs from face videos is a rapidly growing and emerging field with
131 numerous recent publications (Poh et al., 2010; De Haan and Jeanne, 2013; Wang et al., 2017; Tulyakov
132 et al., 2016). The medical measurement of the HR typically relies on the optical measuring technique known
133 as photoplethysmography (PPG) (Zaunseder et al., 2018). This technique capitalizes on human blood
134 circulation, where blood's light absorption exceeds that of surrounding tissue. Consequently, variations
135 in blood volume influence light transmission or reflectance accordingly (Tamura et al., 2014). A PPG
136 sensor, commonly used for measuring the human pulse rate, is placed directly on the skin to optically detect
137 changes in blood volume (Tamura et al., 2014). Remote photoplethysmography employs the same principle,
138 allowing for contactless HR measurements using a standard RGB camera (Zaunseder et al., 2018). In this
139 technique, the continuous change in skin color, resulting from blood flow through the circulatory system, is
140 analyzed by rPPG methods to determine HR (Poh et al., 2010; De Haan and Jeanne, 2013; Wang et al.,
141 2017; Tulyakov et al., 2016).

142 To robustly extract an rPPG signal, irrespective of the subject's skin tone and non-white illumination
143 conditions, the Plane-Orthogonal-to-Skin Transformation (POS) (Wang et al., 2017) of the rPPG signal has
144 been developed for pre-processing the input video sequence.

145 Given that global model-based methods may be susceptible to noise, compression artifacts, or masking,
146 recent rPPG-related publications leverage deep neural networks for HR extraction from video data (Chen
147 and McDuff, 2018; Yu et al., 2019, 2020). Yang et al. (2021) conducted a comparative study of three neural
148 networks (Deepphys (Chen and McDuff, 2018), rPPGNet (Yu et al., 2019), and Physnet (Yu et al., 2020))
149 against model-based approaches (independent component analysis (ICA) (Poh et al., 2010), CHROM
150 (De Haan and Jeanne, 2013), and POS (Wang et al., 2017)) using the publicly available UBFC-rPPG
151 dataset (Bobbia et al., 2019). In these experiments, under constant lighting conditions, deep-learning-based
152 approaches outperformed model-based ones. However, model-based approaches (ICA, CHROM, and POS)
153 exhibited more accurate and robust results in varying lighting conditions (Yang et al., 2021).

154 The locally analyzed rPPG signal extracted from videos is visualized based on amplitude, velocity, or
155 signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) maps (Kossack et al., 2019b; Yang Jun, Guthier B, 2015; Zaunseder et al.,
156 2018). Particularly, blood flow in facial videos has been scrutinized (Yang Jun, Guthier B, 2015; Kossack
157 et al., 2019b,a), where blood flow velocity is calculated from the relative phase shift of the frequency
158 component corresponding to HR in the frequency domain. These methods assume that the difference
159 between neighboring phase values directly corresponds to the velocity at that point.

160 Beyond medical applications (Schraven et al., 2023; Kossack et al., 2023), rPPG analysis has also been
161 employed to detect presentation attacks on authentication systems (Kossack et al., 2022). In multiple studies,
162 rPPG methods are applied to facial videos to discern whether the face is covered by a mask (Li et al., 2017;
163 Kossack et al., 2019a; Yu et al., 2021b). However, deepfake detection proposes another challenge, and as
164 described in Section 2.1, discrepancies between images resulting from deepfake generation disrupt the
165 natural color variations in the skin induced by the heartbeat.

3 METHODS AND DATA

166 We propose a pipeline for extracting and analyzing physiologically related signals, specifically focusing
167 on those associated with the cardiovascular cycle, which typically occur in the frequency range of 0.7 Hz
168 to 3 Hz. To ensure the accurate detection of these signals, the pipeline requires an input video showing
169 the face of a single person for at least 10 s. The proposed pipeline incorporates motion compensation
170 techniques and accounts for frequencies introduced by external factors, such as compression or camera
171 properties, to ensure a robust extraction of physiologically related signals. The details of these components
172 are discussed in the following two sections.

173 Following the components of our pipeline, we describe the data used for the experiments. This includes
174 the dataset of videos and ECG data that we captured, the method used to generate deepfakes and finally an
175 external dataset that was used for evaluation.

176 3.1 Reference Face and Temporal Alignment

177 We focus on global rPPG signals over time, specifically the averaged color changes across various spatial
178 positions on the facial surface. To ensure accurate signal extraction, it is essential to compensate for any
179 movements made by the person in the video. To achieve this, each frame of the input video is aligned with
180 a reference face by detecting facial landmarks using MediaPipe (Google, 2022). These landmarks form the
181 basis for Delaunay triangulation (de Berg et al., 2008), generating a 2D mesh over the facial region. The
182 reference 2D mesh consists of 918 triangles, and serves as a foundation for tracking and stabilizing the
183 facial movements across the video. While this approach is easy to implement, it does not consider motion
184 blur, and the accuracy of the registration is constrained by the facial landmarks. To further enhance this
185 important process, we will extend our method in the future by using the approach proposed by Seibold
186 et al. (2017) for removing motion blur and Seibold et al. (2024) for a pixel-wise registration.

187 In each input frame, we track the detected facial landmarks and use the 2D mesh to warp each triangle to
188 its corresponding reference position. This warping process aligns the facial features from the input video
189 to the reference face, as illustrated in Figure 1. The outcome is a motion-compensated image sequence
190 that serves as the foundation for our subsequent analysis, ensuring that the extracted rPPG signals are not
191 affected by facial movements.

Figure 1. Illustration of the temporal alignment process. A reference mesh, composed of 918 triangles formed from MediaPipe facial landmarks, (center) is used to spatially warp each frame from the video sequence (top) to a reference position (bottom).

192 3.2 Encoding of Heart Rate Related Features

193 To extract heart rates, we perform a global analysis of the entire video to obtain a single robust reference
 194 rPPG signal, which is associated with the subject's pulse signal (Kossack et al., 2021). For rPPG calculation,
 195 we apply the Plane-to-Orthogonal skin (POS) transformation (Wang et al., 2017) on a 10 s window, i.e.,
 196 including 300 frames. A preliminary analysis about the optimal window length showed a standard deviation
 197 of the differences between extracted HR and ground truth for the 10 s window of 1.39 bpm, increasing to
 198 3.38 bpm, 3.76 bpm, and 4.15 bpm for 8 s, 6 s, and 5 s windows, respectively. The entire video is processed
 199 by sliding this window over the video duration with a step size of one frame, ensuring continuous analysis
 200 and accurate pulse signal extraction.

201 After processing the entire video sequence, the output signal is normalized and filtered with a fifth-order
 202 Butterworth digital band-pass filter with a frequency range between 0.7 Hz and 3.0 Hz (corresponding to
 203 a HR of 42 bpm to 180 bpm). This filtering produces the final rPPG signals. For each time step, we then
 204 transform rPPG signal from the time domain to the frequency domain using a fast Fourier transform (FFT),
 205 mapping the signal magnitudes across all time steps for further analysis.

206 This processing is applied to the entire face region to capture physiologically relevant signals, as well as
 207 to two homogeneous square regions in the background to collect image noise information, see Figure 2.
 208 The two background regions are averaged during transformation, resulting in a single FFT map for the
 209 background. The two FFT maps - one from the face and one from the background - are then subtracted
 210 based on their intensities to generate a background-free FFT map that focuses on the physiologically
 211 induced signals.

212 To determine the HR signal over the entire video duration, the highest magnitude in the subtraction
 213 FFT map is identified, and based on this peak, the HR for each time instant is extracted through a single
 214 optimization step.

Figure 2. Heart rate extraction pipeline. From the registered video sequence, we calculate a global rPPG signal of the face as well as the background. Following, we determine the magnitudes in frequency space for each signal over time. To robustly extract the heart rate both signals are 'subtracted'.

215 3.3 Captured Dataset

216 Given that many of the most popular datasets for deepfake analysis are several years old and deepfake
 217 generation techniques have advanced significantly, we created a fully controlled, high-quality dataset
 218 to ensure optimal compression and realism. To validate the functionality of our method, we collected
 219 recordings of twelve individuals, representing diverse genders, ages and ethnic background in a controlled
 220 studio environment. The recordings were captured with participants positioned in front of a white
 221 background, under uniform lighting provided by white LED illumination. For each participant, 10-20
 222 frontal view recordings were taken, with the head centered throughout the video. During each recording,
 223 participants were asked to perform a range of activities, including talking, reading, and interacting with
 224 the recording supervisor. All participants provided written consent for the use of their recordings in this
 225 experiment and its subsequent publication.

226 We used an industry RGB camera¹ to capture the video recordings. The recordings vary in length, ranging
 227 from 10 s up to several minutes, with a frame-rate of 25 fps and a resolution of 2448×2048 pixels. In
 228 addition to the RGB video, we measured the ECG and PPG of selected subjects. These physiological
 229 signals were used to calculate the heart rate (HR) as ground truth for our analysis. Selected frames from
 230 our dataset are shown in Figure 3(a).

231 3.4 Creation of High-quality Deepfakes

232 Publicly available datasets have not kept pace with the rapid development in deepfake technology as
 233 new techniques and architectures continuously emerge, leading to increasingly realistic and higher-quality
 234 deepfakes. This progress likely impacts previous assumptions about deepfakes, particularly the notion that
 235 they do not contain HR-related signals. As deepfake generation methods improve, it becomes necessary to
 236 reassess these conclusions in light of more sophisticated and physiologically accurate manipulations.

237 To generate our own set of high-quality deepfakes, we employed a dual-decoder autoencoder architecture
 238 along with an advanced blending procedure, as described in (Beckmann et al., 2023). Unlike a standard
 239 autoencoder with a single decoder to reconstruct the input image, this model utilizes two decoders. Each
 240 decoder is trained to reconstruct the input image but with the identity of a specific person respectively, the

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Figure 3. A subset of our recorded data representing six participants (a) and a correlating subset of generated deepfakes (b).

241 source and target person. During training, the autoencoder is fed with pairs of images of the source and
242 target person. Once trained, the model can be used to swap faces in images and, accordingly, in videos.
243 The advanced blending procedure enhances quality of the deepfakes by modifying the mask used for
244 blending. Specifically, the mask is adjusted to create a greater distance between the edges of the face and
245 the boundaries of the mask by ‘squeezing’ it by approximately 15 pixels on each side. This adjustment
246 excludes non-facial regions from the blending process, thereby reducing blending artifacts at the boundaries
247 and improving the overall realism of the generated deepfakes.

248 Following data collection, we created various identity pairs and trained a separate deepfake autoencoder
249 for each pair. Using these autoencoders, we performed face swaps between all videos for each identity
250 pair, generating a total of 858 identity-specific deepfake videos and 156 unaltered counterparts. Figure 3(b)
251 shows examples of our deepfakes. For more details on the used method see Beckmann et al. (2023).

252 In addition to these deep fakes, we generated additional ones using the open-source tool DeepFaceLive
253 (DFL) (Petrov, 2023). This tool was developed for real-time face swapping. It requires a driver video and
254 swaps the face in the video with that of a target face model, while maintaining the driver’s expression and
255 head pose. A set of target face models is provided by the tool. We used four of these provided face models
256 to generate 32 deep fake videos. These videos are used in our experiments to show that the rPPG signal of
257 a deep fake is similar to that of its driver video and also to our fakes generated using the same driver video.

258 3.5 External Data

259 In addition to our own dataset, which includes videos with ECG data and corresponding deepfakes, we
260 also utilized publicly available datasets to enhance the scope of our analysis. First, we used the deepfakes
261 generated in Beckmann et al. (2023) based on the ‘actors’ subset of the deepfake detection dataset (Dufour
262 et al., 2019), its corresponding originals as well as the fakes from that dataset based on the same originals.

263 Recognizing that many existing deepfake datasets may have limitations in terms of size and diversity, we
264 selected the KoDF dataset (Kwon et al., 2021), which is designed generalize more effectively to real-world
265 deepfakes compared to other public datasets like FF++ (Rössler et al., 2019) or Celeb-DF (Dang-Nguyen
266 et al., 2020). KoDF contains 403 Korean subjects and a few ten-thousands of real and fake videos. In

Figure 4. This illustration presents two pairs of genuine and fake videos. On the left of each example, frames from each video sequence are displayed. On the right, the extracted reference rPPG signal is plotted for each paired fake and original video. Additionally, the measured heart rate of the person recorded is displayed.

267 addition, KoDF includes six synthesis models for deepfake creation, which brings a large diversity of fakes
 268 to the set; in our study, we utilized four of these six methods due to fake quality.

269 Finally, we selected 45 videos from the KoDF dataset and generated an additional 45 Deepfake videos
 270 using the Picsi.Ai platform², leveraging its available synthesis methods.

4 RESULTS

271 4.1 Signal Analysis

272 In the initial phase of our analysis, we focused on our own dataset, where we successfully extracted
 273 meaningful heart rate (HR) signals from both genuine and deepfake videos. In all cases, the detected HR
 274 corresponded to the face of the subject in the video, regardless of whether the video was real or a deepfake.

275 The average signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the extracted HR was significantly higher in the original
 276 videos compared to the deepfake videos with values of -1.97 dB for genuine and -3.35 dB for deepfakes.
 277 This difference in SNR highlights the lower quality of rPPG signals in deepfakes, likely due to artifacts
 278 introduced during the generation process. As all participants were seated during the recordings and made
 279 only slight movements, it is reasonable to assume that the resting heart rate (normally between 60 bpm to
 280 90 bpm) was detected for all participants. A higher HR was only measured for two participants, but this
 281 was consistent across all recordings and verified by the ECG measurements, suggesting the reliability of
 282 our extraction process. The results of our analysis on four videos, two fake and two genuine, are exemplary
 283 depicted in Figure 4.

284 For the videos with a captured PPG reference signal and deepfakes based on these videos, we further
 285 analyzed the rPPG in time domain. We calculated the Pearson correlation coefficients for the PPG and

² <https://www.picsi.ai>

286 rPPG signals for the genuine videos. Since no ground truth PPG signal can be measured for the deepfakes,
 287 the signal from the underlying driver video is used instead. In addition to the correlation, we calculated the
 288 Mean Squared Error (MSE) for the rPPG signals, using the PPG signals as ground truth. Before calculating
 289 the MSE, the mean and variance of both signals were normalized to zero and one, respectively. The results
 290 are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Correlation and deviation of rPPG to PPG signal as well as the absolute difference of the heart rate (HR) between detected and ground truth. The rPPG signal of the deep fake videos generated with DeepFaceLive (DFL) shows a similarly strong correlation to the measured PPG signal as the rPPG signal for the genuine videos. The correlation for the rPPG signal of the deep fake videos generated with the methods of (Beckmann et al., 2023) is slightly weaker but still moderate. The MSE is in a similar range for all types of videos.

291 For all types of videos, there is a moderate to strong correlation in most samples. The correlation between
 292 the PPG and rPPG signals for the genuine videos and the DeepFaceLive (DFL) fakes shows a similar
 293 distribution, while the correlation for deepfakes generated with the method of (Beckmann et al., 2023) is
 294 slightly lower. These high correlations between the rPPG signals of the deepfakes and the ground truth PPG
 295 signal of the driver videos show that these fakes replicate the rPPG signal of the driver videos. This point
 296 is further supported by the HR gained from the rPPG signal. The absolute difference to the ground truth
 297 across all videos and time periods is on average 1.80 bpm, 1.85 bpm and 3.24 bpm for the genuine videos,
 298 the (Beckmann et al., 2023) and DFL fakes, respectively. It should be noted that rPPG signal extraction
 299 from videos includes, alongside the PPG-related signal, additional components induced by body motion
 300 and other noise sources, and thus cannot perfectly reflect a true PPG signal.

301 In addition to comparisons with ground truth PPG signals, we calculated the Pearson correlation
 302 coefficients between these deepfakes and their underlying driver videos. The results are shown in Figure 6.
 303 While the correlation for videos generated with DFL is strong in most cases, the correlation for those
 304 generated with the method of (Beckmann et al., 2023) is moderate for most videos. This provides further
 305 evidence that deepfakes mimic the rPPG signal of the driver video.

306 Building on these results, we further analyzed the generated deepfakes to investigate the origin of their
 307 rPPG signals. In the majority of cases, the rPPG signals in the deepfakes closely mirrored those of the
 308 original source videos, with only minor variations observed. When comparing the HR measured in the
 309 genuine videos with those from their deepfake counterparts, we found that the global HR in the deepfake
 310 videos was remarkably similar to the HR of the original source recordings, as well as to the measured ECG

Figure 6. Correlation and deviation of rPPG signals of deepfakes to their underlying driver video's rPPG signal. The rPPG signals of the deepfakes generated with DeepFaceLive (DFL) show a strong correlation to the rPPG signal of the underlying driver videos in most cases, while those for the deepfakes generated with the method of (Beckmann et al., 2023) are weaker but, on average, still moderate. The DFL deepfakes outperform also in terms of MSE those of (Beckmann et al., 2023).

Figure 7. Heart Rates of different videos. In each plot the extracted HR of the original video (red), the recorded ECG signal (yellow) and a created high-quality deepfake (blue) using the original video as source video is shown.

311 ground truth, see examples in Figure 7. For all fakes in our dataset, we found a high correlation to the HR
 312 of the original driving video, see Figure 8. The average correlation between the HR of the fakes created by
 313 using the method of (Beckmann et al., 2023) is $\bar{r} = 0.57$ (median $r = 0.55$) and for the fakes generated
 314 with DFL $\bar{r} = 0.82$ (median $r = 0.89$). For the other fakes (KoDF dataset, both methods on actor subset),
 315 the correlation is above $r > 0.4$. However, for the public available FF++ fakes, the deviation is remarkably
 316 high (min $r = -0.23$ to max $r = 0.91$). These findings confirm that the heart rate signals in high-quality
 317 deepfakes are often inherited from the source video, further complicating the task of distinguishing between
 318 real and fake content based solely on global HR analysis.

319 The FFT maps visualize that the rPPG signal, which can be traced back to physiological properties,
 320 clearly originates from the source video. Figures 9 and 10 show two examples with a set of six FFT maps,
 321 the background, face and subtraction FFT maps of an original video and an deepfake, where the original
 322 served as source. The extracted HRs for both examples can be found in Figure 7.

323 Example *ID_04_0100* demonstrates the influence of our proposed background analysis on signal detection.
 324 In this instance, a strong noise signal around 150 bpm is detectable in the background. Due to the nature
 325 of deepfake generation, this noise signal is also present in all fakes where that capture served as source,
 326 resulting in a high correlation between the FFT maps of original and deepfakes (with a correlation of

Figure 8. Correlation and MSE of Heart Rates (HR) of the deepfakes to their underlying driver video’s HR. The correlation of the HRs of the deepfakes generated with DeepFaceLive show a strong correlation, while those for the deepfakes generated with the method of (Beckmann et al., 2023) are moderate.

Figure 9. FFT maps of capturing *ID_04_0100*. A similar HR can be detected in both cases, original source and deepfake video with about 59 bpm. The correlations between the original and deepfake FFT maps shows a strong relationship for all three map pairs: 0.96 for background, 0.77 for face, and 0.78 for subtraction map.

327 0.96). In the original face video, the physiological signal (at about 59 bpm) is twice as strong as the
 328 background noise signal (at 150 bpm), making it easy to extract. However, in the deepfake face, the HR
 329 and noise signals are of comparable magnitudes, complicating clear pulse extraction. This issue is resolved
 330 by incorporating background analysis, as shown in Figure 9.

331 The correlation between the original and deepfake FFT maps increases slightly, 0.7667 for the face FFT
 332 maps to 0.7826 for the subtraction maps, further emphasizing that the rPPG signal in the deepfake originates
 333 from the source video. This strong relationship between the original and deepfake signals extends to cases
 334 where the background signals in the deepfakes differ more significantly from the originals, reinforcing the
 335 notion that deepfakes inherit their rPPG signals from the driver video. cf. Figure 10.

Figure 10. FFT maps of capturing *ID_11_1100*. A similar HR can be detected in both cases, original source and deepfake video with about 71 bpm. The correlations between the original and deepfake FFT maps shows a moderate to strong relationship for all three map pairs: 0.50 for background (moderate relationship), 0.91 for face (strong), and 0.89 for subtraction map (strong).

336 Both examples clearly demonstrate that, in the analysis of the face region in deepfakes, the background
 337 signal (induced by noise, compression, etc.) plays a significantly stronger role, as the transferred HR signal
 338 is reproduced with less intensity compared to the original video. This is also reflected in the corresponding
 339 SNRs (see above). Due to the weaker transmission and artificial replication of the pulse signal, a strong
 340 correlation between the original and deepfake signal is not always observed, see Figure 11 as example
 341 for a moderate relationship between original source and deepfake subtraction maps with a correlation of
 342 0.53. However, upon closer examination, a trace of the original video's HR signal can still be detected
 343 in the faked face. This 'signal trace' underscores that, despite noise and degradation, elements of the
 344 physiological signal from the source video remain present in the deepfake.

345 4.2 Analysis on External Data

346 Given the limited size of our dataset, we extended of HR analysis to the KoDF and FF++ dataset.
 347 Despite varying compression rates and relatively high image noise, we were able to consistently extract
 348 HR signals from all genuine videos. Although some deepfake videos presented challenges due to noise and
 349 compression artifacts, we were still able to extract signals in most cases that could be associated with HR,

Figure 11. FFT subtraction maps of (a) capturing ID_004_0110 and (b) a related deepfake. In the original FFT map, a HR can be identified clearly at around 65 bpm. The FFT subtraction map of the deepfake is more noisy but the HR of the underlying original is detectable as well. The correlation between both maps is moderate with 0.53.

350 cf. Figure 8. However, as the datasets do not include the participants' actual HR data, we were unable to
 351 validate these extracted HR signals against ground truth measurements.

352 A closer look to quality parameter (Table 1) shows a extremely low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the
 353 extracted HRs for the external datasets, especially for FF++, while the deviation of the HR over time
 354 is high although all videos involve individuals who are at rest and should therefore have a stable pulse.
 355 This indicates that for a certain amount of videos, the detected HR is not plausible, i.e., not related to the
 356 real HR, although we have selected the videos with best signal quality and analyzed the corresponding
 357 deepfakes. It is important to note, that it is not possible for the KoDF dataset to identify the exact driver
 358 video used for each fake. Therefore, we only looked at whether it is possible to identify a physiologically
 359 meaningful HR in both the original and the fake videos. Here, similar results as with our dataset could be
 360 achieved, cf. Figure 12. For the deepfakes, a signal which can be related to a HR is in most cases detectable.
 361 For further examples of FFT maps of deepfakes from the KoDF dataset are shown in Figure 13 in the
 362 Appendix.

5 DISCUSSION

363 As discussed in Section 3.5, numerous datasets have been developed to support deepfake research, such
 364 as the DeepFake Detection Challenge Dataset (Dolhansky et al., 2020), FF++ (Rössler et al., 2019), and
 365 Celeb-DF (Dang-Nguyen et al., 2020). These datasets have significantly advanced deepfake detection
 366 techniques. However, few authors have explored deepfake detection through the analysis of physiologically
 367 related signals, such as rPPG. Despite their importance, public datasets present several challenges when
 368 used for analyzing rPPG signals in the context of deepfake detection as rPPG is sensitive to video quality.

Table 1. Signal-to-Noise ratio (SNR) and standard deviation (STD) of the extracted HR signal for all included data.

Method	Beckmann et al. (2023)	DFL	KoDF	Actor our Fakes	Actor FF++ Fakes
SNR Originals [dB]	5.595	8.947	4.470	2.951	1.852
SNR Fakes [dB]	3.566	7.838	3.027	2.730	2.345
STD Originals [bpm]	5.033	2.779	7.892	6.929	8.291
STD Fakes [bpm]	7.300	2.245	8.609	8.931	8.833

Figure 12. FFT maps of a deepfake taken from the KoDF dataset. The extracted HR is about 69 bpm.

369 Many deepfake datasets suffer from compression artifacts, low resolution, inconsistent frame rates,
 370 high background noise, and challenging illumination settings D'Amelio et al. (2023); Kwon et al. (2021).
 371 These factors can substantially degrade the quality of rPPG signals, making it difficult to reliably extract
 372 physiological features (Wang et al., 2024; Zaunseder et al., 2018; McDuff et al., 2017). Consequently, the
 373 utility of rPPG analysis in deepfake detection has been limited, particularly in datasets where video quality
 374 is compromised.

375 Previous studies (Çiftçi et al., 2024; Qi et al., 2020; Ciftci et al., 2020b,a; Hernandez-Ortega et al.,
 376 2020) concluded that deepfakes do not exhibit a detectable heartbeat (Boccignone et al., 2022), suggesting
 377 that this could be used as a reliable marker for deepfake detection. However, much of this research was
 378 conducted on datasets of low image quality. In contrast, our study reveals that for recent and high-quality
 379 deepfakes, such as those generated using the method described in Beckmann et al. (2023), DeepFaceLive
 380 or present in the KoDF dataset, it is possible to robustly detect a HR signal that originates from the source
 381 (driver) video. Our experiments demonstrated that deepfakes can exhibit realistic heart rates, contradicting
 382 previous findings. Specifically, in all fake videos from our dataset and most videos from the KoDF dataset,
 383 valid HR signals were successfully extracted. This indicates that solely relying on the analysis of global
 384 HR signals is no longer sufficient to detect deepfakes.

385 Another significant challenge in existing deepfake datasets is the lack of reference measurements, such
 386 as concurrent ECG or PPG sensor readings, which are crucial for validating the accuracy of extracted rPPG
 387 signals. Without these ground truth data, it becomes difficult to assess the reliability of physiological signal
 388 extraction and, consequently, the conclusions drawn from them.

389 To improve the utility of physiological signals for deepfake detection, we propose shifting from global
 390 HR analysis to locally resolved signals within the face. Recent advances in video-based vital sign analysis
 391 have moved toward capturing local pulse signals from specific facial regions Kossack et al. (2019b, 2021),
 392 which better reflect the anatomical blood flow patterns of the human face. By leveraging these localized
 393 physiological patterns, we aim to enhance both the robustness and interpretability of deepfake detection.
 394 Building on this idea, we performed initial experiments where we extracted rPPG-related feature maps
 395 from a subset of our dataset following the approach described in Schraven et al. (2023) and trained an
 396 EfficientNet-B4 model as a convolutional deepfake detector (Tan and Le, 2019). Our preliminary results
 397 (AUROC score of 87.4%) show promising results that these local maps can be used for deepfake detection.
 398 Using the rPPG-based features improves interpretability by providing more understandable features, but
 399 the detector itself lacks transparency by design. To overcome this issue, we adapt in the future the concept

400 proposed by Seibold et al. (2021), which leads to detectors that accurately determines which part of the
401 input contributes to the prediction that an input is a forgery.

6 CONCLUSION

402 In conclusion, our study demonstrates that high-quality deepfakes exhibit rPPG signals that correspond
403 to the HR of the source (driver) video. By comparing the different PPG signals and analyzing the FFT
404 maps as well as the extracted HRs and its correlations, we confirmed that the globally derived rPPG signal
405 originates from the driving video, rather than being artificially generated. This finding challenges previous
406 assumptions that deepfakes inherently lack valid physiological signals, revealing the limitations of using
407 simple HR analysis for detecting high-quality deepfakes.

408 One of the key contributions of our study is the demonstration that HR signals in deepfakes can closely
409 match those of the source video, making traditional global HR-based detection methods insufficient for
410 distinguishing between real and fake content. By performing our analysis not only on our own dataset but
411 also on fakes created with DeepFaceLive and from the KoDF dataset, we confirmed the generalization of
412 our findings, showing that even older deepfake datasets contain valid HR signals.

413 To address this limitation, we propose leveraging local blood flow information for deepfake detection.
414 Preliminary experiments indicate that this localized analysis holds significant promise for improving
415 detection accuracy. As part of ongoing work, we are further refining this approach, which also offers the
416 added benefit of enhanced explainability. Visualizing local blood flow patterns could provide clearer insight
417 into the decision-making process of detection algorithms. Another important factor in ensuring robust
418 detection is the availability of good and diverse training data. An attacker may attempt to mimic blood flow
419 patterns to evade detection; therefore, we plan to enhance our deepfake dataset using style-transfer with a
420 temporal component by extending the work on improved image forgeries of Seibold et al. (2019).

421 In summary, our contributions include: (1) providing evidence that deepfakes can exhibit realistic heart
422 rate signals, (2) highlighting the insufficiency of global HR analysis for detecting high-quality deepfakes,
423 and (3) proposing the use of localized rPPG signals to enhance both the robustness and explainability of
424 deepfake detection. Our approach could serve as a valuable complement to existing techniques, with the
425 potential to improve the security and integrity of multimedia content across platforms.

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APPENDIX

Figure 13. FFT maps of three different deepfakes taken from KoDF dataset.